

REVISITING DORAH PASS: A CULTURAL AND STRATEGIC CORRIDOR BETWEEN CHITRAL AND CENTRAL ASIA

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15781299>

Received	Revised	Accepted	Published
06 May, 2025	06 June, 2025	21 June, 2025	30 June, 2025

ABSTRACT

This research paper explores the historical and contemporary significance of the Dorah Pass, a strategically located border in the northwest of Chitral, Khyber-Pakhtunkhwa. The Dorah border connects Pakistan with Afghan-Badakhshan, which then provides direct access to Tajikistan and other countries in Central Asia. Also known locally as the Shah Salim or Shaisidim, the Dorah Pass lies approximately 485 km from the capital city of Islamabad and has historically served as a key route on the ancient Silk Road, facilitating mass migration, trade, and religious movements. The pass continues to hold cultural relevance even today, with communities on both sides sharing deep-rooted ways of life and tradition. This study aims to offer a comprehensive overview of Dorah's cultural, historical, and geopolitical importance for Pakistan, Afghanistan, and Central Asia.

INTRODUCTION

Chitral now consists of two districts of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan, and is surrounded by some of the tallest mountain ranges of the *Hindukush*, situated in the extreme North of Pakistan near the Afghanistan border. Chitral has remained an independent princely state for centuries, with its economy, language, and culture. During British colonization, in the late nineteenth century, it became a part of British India. It was a princely state till 1947, which acceded to being a part of Pakistan in the same year. The rule of *Mehtar* (ruler) came to an end in 1954, and power was henceforth exercised by the political agent posted at Chitral. The state merged as a district with Pakistan in 1969. Chitral has almost 32 different subsidiary valleys connecting to the main city through different link routes. Valleys like Broghil, Laspur, and Arkari are very far away, and people are facing difficulties in accessing basic human facilities, and this long distance and remoteness also create challenges to administrative grip over the scattered and isolated areas. Being in the extreme north geographically, it is a heavy snowfall zone,

and therefore most of its parts face harsh weather conditions, particularly in winter.

History shows that Chitral has been inhabited for many thousands of years. Its people belong to over a dozen different cultures and speak more than 12 languages and dialects. The major language of Chitral is *Kohwar* (Chetrari war), while Urdu is also used as the national language in the district. Some other prominent local languages are Wakhi, Yadgha, Pashto, Bamedi, Kalasha, Gawarbati, etc. As a result of its unique location and historical links with Central Asia, its materials and nonmaterial cultures bear a number of external influences. The population of Chitral was about 497,800 according to the 2017 census.

Like Sawat, Hunza, Gilgit, and the other beautiful valleys of Pakistan, Chitral has also tourist attraction features, and thousands of tourists and explorers travel to Chitral every year. Particularly, the presence of the most ancient *Kalash* community in Chitral is no less than a blessing for the soil of Chitral, which attracts a huge number of national and international

researchers, explorers, and tourists. And if the infrastructure of the area is developed, we will see an enormous influx of tourists moving to Chitral and its surroundings.

Chitral's Border Passes

Chitral shares almost 30 borders with its surroundings. Starting with the Dorah pass and Broghil pass, which connect Chitral with Badakhshan (the Wakhan Corridor of Afghanistan) in the North, Shandur pass connects with Gilgit Baltistan in the Northeast. As the map of the Chitral region below depicts, it shares borders with Swat in the East, and

Lawari Pass connects with Dir in the South, Arandu Pass connects with Kunar (Afghanistan's Province) in the South, and Begusht and Kalasha valleys connect with Nuristan (Afghanistan's Province) in the Northwest. Besides these famous passes, there are several minor passes like Akram Pass, Anogole Pass, and Birzin Pass that have been used by migrants, invaders, preachers, and tourists historically. Among all the passes, Dorah, Broghil, and Arandu have been the busiest passes for centuries. These routes have been frequently used for different purposes like trade, preaching, and migrations in different times and periods.

Dorah Boarder: A Historical Background

As it has been mentioned above that Dorah had been the busiest, closest, and safest route for the hajj caravans, invaders, traders, travellers, migrants, and preachers between Central Asia and Pakistan throughout history. Its altitude is almost 14800 ft / 4112m, and it is located along the Durand line border and crosses the Hindukush Mountain range (Faizi,1991). It's estimated distance from Islamabad is almost 485 km. According to the survey by the Provincial Government. KPK, the distance from Islamabad to Eshkashim (the border town of Tajikistan) via Chitral Dorah Pass is almost half (560 km) as compared to the Islamabad-Torkham-Kabul-

Tajikistan route (1050 km) to the same border. In the case of constructing a tunnel at Dorah Pass, this distance will further decrease. These reports also reveal that to connect with Central Asia, through the Dorah pass, its 85% route crosses through Pakistani territory, while in the case of Torkham, 77% of the route crosses through Afghanistan, which makes Dorah an ideal point for connectivity. In the recent development, Govt. of Pakistan and the CPEC authority have taken the decision to build an alternative CPEC route, Chitral via Shandur, and in that connection, the Dorah border in close proximity will further create wider opportunities for the economic relationship between China and

Central Asia at the same time. (Letter and Interview of Mr. Wazir Zada Ex. Provincial Minister Khyber Pakhtunkhwa)

One of the very positive aspects of this border is, it has very little distance from the populated areas on both sides. In Chitral, the closest village to Dorah is Shah Salim Gobor, which is almost 20 km away, while the Sanglich Badakhshan (the closest populated area on the Badakhshan side) is around 40 km away from the main border. Mr. Sultan Mehmood, who served as an Ex. Provincial Community Development Manager with AKDN in Badakhshan and frequently travelled through the Dorah Pass, shared that a person departing on foot from Gobor early in the morning can reach Sanglich by evening the same day. However, when using a vehicle, the journey from Shah Salim (Chitral) to Sanglich (Badakhshan) takes approximately four hours. A well-known researcher, traveller, and linguist, Morgenstern (1929), who had visited Northern Areas and Chitral, writes, "From Shah Salim, I ascended the Dorah Pass (14800 feet), one of the most important Hindu Kush passes. The Dorah is quite easy, and the distance between inhabited places on both sides is not very great" (p.44).

If we discuss its historical utilization, we see a number of accounts that tell us that it is one of the ancient silk trade routes between Central Asia and China and its surroundings. In addition, people living on both sides of the border have shared similar cultural heritages, traditions, and way of life, which indicates their long-standing relations through this border. Historical accounts tell us about the influences of some great ancient religions in Chitral, particularly Zoroastrians, Buddhism, and Kalasha, which had access to Chitral and Gilgit through some prominent borders like the Dorah and Broghil.

One of the very credible sources is a very old book, *Hudud al-Alam*, written in 372/982AD on Persian geography, which provides comprehensive information about the utilization of the Dorah and Broghil passes. The mentioned book, which is translated by Minorsky (1930), says, "Once in Shughnan (usually merged in Vakhan), the merchants could follow up the stream or cross into Chitral and Gilgit by the well-known passes in the Hindukush (Dora and Baroghil)" (p.364). It evidently shows that in the 10th century these passes were being used by the traders, and this process of communication,

transportation, and travel has continued throughout history. Another Central Asian expert, Wood J., 1841, in his book (*A Personal Narrative of a journey to the sources of the river Oxus, by the route of the Indus, Kabul, and Badakhshan*), while discussing this long trading relationship, says,

... with forty iron pots ...loaded [on] five yobus [packed horse], and made his way to Chitral. Here he [Trader] readily disposed of them, and after investing part of the proceeds in honey, started for the Chinese frontier... where he [trader] safely arrived and sold his Chitral investments to such advantage that he cleared fourteen times the value of his original venture—the forty cast-iron pots. (pp. 290-91)

Besides invasions and business purposes, this border has also been used by famous saints, mystics, and religious preachers in different periods of time. As mentioned earlier that the presence of a few old religions in Chitral has been verified by many prominent historians and writers like Karl Jetmar (1996), Faizi (2005), Ghuran (1962), Baig (2004), and Najeeb (2000). It clearly reveals the arrival of respective preachers from Central Asia to Chitral and Northern Areas to propagate Buddhism, Zoroastrian, and Kalasha's beliefs because it is evident that Central Asia and Ancient Persia have been the center of propagation of these great religions. It is interesting to note here that most of the historians agree that Islam entered Chitral first time from Central Asia through a famous Central Asian Fatimid Ismaili *Dai*, philosopher, and Traveler, Nasir Khusraw, in the 11th Century via the Dorah border. The *Astana* (Ziarat) of Nasir Khusraw in Garam Chashma Chitral is one of the strong evidences of Central Asian religious influence, and ritualistic expressions and living Ismaili traditions attributed to Nasir Khusraw have always been an appealing theme of study for scholars.

In addition to this, we see, different tribes of Chitral had mostly migrated from Badakhshan, Tajikistan, Kazakhstan, and Kyrgyzstan, still having their family linkages, historical connections with Badakhshan, and share common cultural heritage. Their historical connections and travels have also been maintained through these important borders, i.e., Dorah and Broghil. In the 20th Century, a Legendary figure of Chitral, Sher Afzal (an exiled

brother of the Chitrali ruler), also used the Durah border to attack Chitral with the support of the King of Afghanistan, Amir Abdul Rehman. (Muhammad Amin, Chitraltoday). It is astonishing to note here that historically this famous border has remained far away from the world's attention, and for the first time, it came into the world's focus during the former Soviet Union's invasion of Afghanistan.

Road Construction and Trade Relations in the 1980s and early 90s.

During the former Soviet Union's invasion of Afghanistan in the 1980s, the Dorah border played a key role in facilitating the *Mujahideen's* resistance against the Soviet army. As a native of Garam Chashma, Chitral, the author of this paper witnessed the situations and events that unfolded during the 1980s and early 1990s. At that time, Pakistan, in close collaboration with the United States of America and some Arab countries, supported the *Mujahideen* in pushing back the Soviet forces from Afghanistan. The Soviet invasion of Afghanistan was not only an attack on a sovereign nation, but it also posed an existential threat to Pakistan. As Pakistan shares a 2640 km-long border with Afghanistan, the risk of the Soviet war expanding to Pakistan was strongly felt. Therefore, Pakistan's alliance with the US and some Arab nations supported the *Mujahideen's* resistance. Dorah was one of the busiest borders used by the *Mujahideen* to fight against the Soviet forces. This was the time when millions of Afghans migrated to Pakistan through different borders, including Dorah. During the late 1980s, two major ammunition camps were established in Garam Chashma, Chitral, strategically positioned near the Dorah border. These camps served as major supply hubs for providing weapons and logistical support to two different fighting groups in the Badakhshan province of Afghanistan. The author also recalls the catastrophic explosions that destroyed both camps, claiming precious lives of over 40 people working and living near the camps.

During late 80s and early 90s, a jeepable road was constructed from both sides and there was a bilateral business continued, for instance, Afghan used to bring livestock, gemstones, styrax, utensils, carpets, handicrafts, herbal medicines, and a few edible things to Garam Chashma, on the other hand they used to purchase almost all

human necessities like food, cooking oil, sugar, rice, fabrics, etc. According to a report published in a credible online newspaper, Chitralnews, the Dorah (Gobor) route was the largest source of revenue collection for the district council in the form of octroi tax. Till the 1990s full full-loaded vehicles used to travel from Garam Chashma to different parts of Badakhshan, mostly Faizabad. Local drivers used to travel to Afghan-Badakhshan, daily, and there was no compulsion on the borders on any kind of movement. One of the well-known transporters, Mr. Nawab Khan, currently serving as the Chairman of the Union Council, shared his experience as a frequent traveler between Garam Chashma and Badakhshan in an interview:

"It used to be an almost 14-hour journey from Garam Chashma to Faizabad, Badakhshan. Drivers would load various items into their vehicles and navigate the bumpy roads to reach their destination. The route was quite safe and friendly in terms of security. I recall several instances when our vehicles broke down along the way, yet we never faced any security threats." (Interview with Mr. Nawab Khan conducted in 2025)

Contemporary Situations and Govt. Initiatives

The utilization of this border has always been subject to the relations between Pakistan and Afghanistan. Since the USSR's collapse, this border has remained closed for any kind of business, trade, and transportation, while local communication and travel have continued from time to time. During the year 2019, the Government of Pakistan took the initiative to work on the two Cross-transit border trade. i.e., Arandu, and Dorah in Lower Chitral. Later on, due to security issues and the invasion by the Taliban, Afghanistan's situation deteriorated, and this initiative did not take practical implementation. (Interview with Mr. Sartaj, Former Tehsil Nazim of Chitral, conducted in 2025). Moreover, one of the important aspects which we should not ignore is, these kinds of initiatives cannot be materialized until and unless we find security clearance. This is a bitter reality in a country like Pakistan, having huge security concerns on various borders, it is not easy to make decisions at once for any kind of political and economic relations by ignoring security measures.

Conclusion and Recommendations

No one can deny the strategic importance and historical significance of Dorah, keeping in view the contextual realities and contemporary political situations. It shares one of the shortest and safest borders with Badakhshan, which is one of the richest provinces of Afghanistan in terms of minerals and other natural resources. This also connects Pakistan with Central Asian republics via Tajikistan by crossing the very shortest distance in the Wakhan corridor, which is 100 km. Pakistan's Govt and its business community

not only have huge business opportunities in the Badakhshan area, but it will also open new horizons of business prospects in the Central Asian Republics. We can create direct sustainable business linkages with Central Asian Countries, which are rich in natural resources like Gas, Minerals, and Petroleum. On the other hand, Pakistan can have exchange business opportunities like medicines, fabrics, food items, petrochemicals, automobile lubricants, and fruits etc., which have a high demand in Central Asian countries.

Secondly, connecting the Dorah border with the CPEC route will definitely open wonderful opportunities for Pakistan to have economic relationships with China and the Central Asian republics simultaneously. As Islamabad-Dorah-Tajikistan is the shortest route, which passes through 85% of Pakistani territory will provide more business opportunities to the people of Pakistan living around the expected connecting route. There have been several official attempts by the government to construct a road from Chitral to Garam Chahsma-Dorah Pass; however, none of them have materialized successfully. For instance, in 2022, the National Highway Authority (NHA) floated a tender for this route with complete details, but the project was

abruptly halted without any clear or comprehensive justification.

Thirdly, as it is being said that Pakistan is a cultural extension of Central Asia, this connectivity will also offer huge facilitation to our tourism industry when we create better infrastructure for travel and to appreciate the diversity of culture and traditions. It has been observed that most Western tourists want to explore the old Silk-route and wish to travel to all the connected countries by crossing these borders. Certainly, if we become successful in materializing this idea, it will invite people from different parts of the world, which will have a very positive impact on our economy too.

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Interviewed:

- Mr. Wazir Zada (Ex. Provisional Minister)
- Mr. Sultan Mehmood (Ex. Provincial Community Development Manager, AKDN, Badakhshan)
- Mr. Sartaj Ahmad Khan, Ex-Tehsil Nazim Chitral
- Mr. Nawab Khan (Chairman, Union Council Garam Chashma)

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Maps:

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